

CURRICULUM STREAMLINING OF THE BASIC EDUCATION LEARNING CONTINUITY PLAN: AN ASSESSMENT ON THE DEGREE OF IMPLEMENTATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 7

Pages: 761-765

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2001

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12647578

Manuscript Accepted: 06-03-2024

Curriculum Streamlining of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan: An Assessment on the Degree of Implementation

Gledy Mae Valdez-La Corda*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The Department of Education fronted an abrupt shift in the implementation of instruction and learning from physical (face-to-face) classes to distance/blended learning in the midst of the pandemic. The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) was an answer that ought to uphold educational standards and learning outcomes, ensuring that students continue to achieve their learning goals despite the changes in the mode of delivery. Thus, this descriptive-comparative study evaluated the implementation of curriculum streamlining of the BE-LCP among the 28 Senior High School teachers and 5 Learning Area Coordinators with the use of two separate survey questionnaires. While the results show an outstanding implementation of curriculum streamlining of the BE-LCP, a gap exist in teachers' training in crafting learning materials aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). The success with broader curriculum changes highlights the need for additional support in crafting materials aligned with learning competencies. For this reason, it is further recommended that the school leaders should provide emphasis on continued professional development through training and conferences in order to recognize the importance of lifelong learning for the teachers making them abreast of the best practices and innovative educational strategies to enhance their classroom effectiveness.

Keywords: *Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), curriculum streamlining, implementation*

Introduction

Education is one of the most crucial elements needed to navigate the challenges of this generation. Many experts believed that education is powerful enough to change the world. As the society evolves and grows rapidly, education plays a crucial role in shaping the youth, enabling them to become the hope and future leaders of the world. However, this potential depends on the quality of education that each country provides to its students, which, while challenging, is achievable.

When the Philippine government ordered the closure of all educational institutions, the disruptions were sudden, as classes were still in session. At the height of the pandemic, educational institutions introduced remote learning as an alternative solution. This immediate action and strategy aimed to mitigate the impact of the closures while continuing to deliver quality education.

DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2020 was issued to provide clear guidance to all offices, units, schools, and community learning centers (CLCs) of the Department of Education (DepEd), learners and their parents, partners, and stakeholders, the Department developed a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), a package of education interventions that will respond to basic education challenges brought about by the health crisis. ensure learning continuity through K-12 curriculum adjustments, alignment of learning materials, deployment of multiple learning delivery modalities, provision of corresponding training for teachers and school leaders and proper orientation of parents or guardians of learners. Moreover, Arrieta (2020) added that having a learning continuity plan will serve as a guiding principle for the academic community in carrying out their obligations and commitments in providing a conducive online learning environment to the learners.

In addition, the BE-LCP streamlines the K to 12 Curriculum into the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), to be delivered in multiple learning modalities and platforms. The streamlining of the K to 12 Curriculum into the MELCs is an emergency measure to allow instruction amid challenging circumstances to focus on the most essential learning, and to ease the requirements for adapting classroom-based learning resource for distance learning ensuring that students continued to receive a meaningful education despite the limitations imposed by the pandemic. This approach aimed to simplify the curriculum to make it more manageable for remote and blended learning environments, ensuring that both teachers and students could effectively engage with the material while maintaining educational standards and quality. Similarly, Rabor, Barredo, Opinio, and Carmona (2021), states that conducting streamlining of the K to 12 Curriculum into the MELCS aids in focusing on the enhancement of the mastery of learning competencies on the part of the learners.

However, there are major issues that need to be addressed in the streamlining of the BE-LCP and its implementation. Key issues include the abrupt shift of the learning modality which hinders the effective delivery and reception of the curriculum, potentially exacerbating existing educational inequalities. Another is the localization and contextualization that can cause a complication on the uniform implementation of the streamlined curriculum across diverse regions. Ordinario (2022), affirms that due to the abrupt shift of learning modality, not all learners were able to adapt and were reached out.

This research then aimed to assess and describe the degree of implementation on the curriculum streamlining of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) of the teachers and school leaders of the Senior High School Department of a private university

at Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess and describe the degree of implementation on the curriculum streamlining of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) of the teachers and learning area coordinators of the Senior High School Department. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what degree of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) implementation relative to curriculum streamlining?
2. Is there a significant difference in the overall implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) by teachers and learning area coordinators?

Literature Review

Curriculum streamlining

The study of Manire (2021) observed that the first phase of the curriculum management aspect of BE-LCP evolved in the adaptation and adjustments made for the most essential part of the curriculum and learning content which is the streamlining of the K-12 curriculum. However, all of the goals and objectives carried out by this relatively new curriculum cannot be accomplished due to the risks posed by the pandemic. This is the reason for the creation of the Most Essential Learning Competencies. MELCs is generally defined as “competencies necessary to develop a learner’s practical and lifelong skills for learning amidst a crisis” (Department of Education, 2020b, par. 3.2). Hence, monitoring and evaluation are key to the strict implementation of this streamlined curriculum. Having said this, the Department of Education has created a Learning Resource and Platform Committee that will continue to monitor and evaluate the implementation of the streamlined curriculum which manifested in the document, “our teachers and school leaders shall be capacitated to implement and manage the adoption of multi-modal learning delivery models’, moreover, “educators are encouraged to make use of innovative strategies to deliver distance learning in a larger magnitude.”

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-comparative qualitative method. Descriptive design is used in research studies that aim to determine the distribution of one or more variables without considering any causal or other hypotheses (Aggarwal & Ranganathan, 2019). On the other hand, comparative design is used to determine and quantify relationships between two or more variables by observing different groups that either by choice or circumstances is exposed to different treatments (Bukhari, 2011).

In addition, the quantitative approach determined the level of implementation of the BE-LCP. The same approach also assessed the streamlining of the curriculum particularly on attendance to orientation/mentoring on curriculum review, contextualization, localization and implementation and MELCs unpacking and sub-tasking.

Respondents

The study utilized purposive-population sampling. The respondents were the Senior High School teachers and learning area coordinators of Senior High School Department of a private university at Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.; there were 28 teachers and 5 learning area coordinators for the academic year 2021-2022. The participants of the study are teachers and learning area coordinators for the academic year 2021-2022; regardless of their employment status, highest educational attainment, and years of service, all of the faculty members of SMUSHS participated in this study.

Instruments

The research instrument was developed by the researcher. It is a survey questionnaire used to assess the degree of implementation of the BE-LCP. The researcher-made survey questionnaire was content – validated by an expert in the fields of statistics and research. It is highly accepted in terms of suitability and appropriateness of items and reported a reliability index of Cronbach $\alpha = .97$ which is an excellent coefficient.

It is a six-item questionnaire that validated the teachers’ attendance to orientation/mentoring on curriculum review, contextualization, localization and implementation and MELCs unpacking and sub-tasking. It is a 4-point Likert-type scale, with anchors ranging from 4 (To a Very Large Extent) to 1 (To a Small Extent).

For the learning area coordinators, the questionnaire validated the conduct of school-based orientation/mentoring on curriculum review, contextualization, localization and implementation as well as the conduct of online trainings workshop on crafting MELCs-based activity sheets. It is a 4-point Likert-type scale, with anchors ranging from 4 (Outstanding/Full Implementation) to 1 (Fair Implementation).

Procedure

The researcher initiated the conduct of the study by forwarding a communication letter to the Senior High School Principal. Upon approval, the researcher individually sent the Google Form to the teachers and learning area coordinators with an attached informed consent form.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher asked the consent of the respondents to participate in the data-gathering process by signing an Informed Consent Form (ICF). The primary goal of data collection was to generate answers to the research problems. After the data analysis, the researcher discarded the responses in the Google Form.

Results and Discussion

This section analyzes and interprets the key findings of the study. The results include two sections: the degree of implementation of the BE-LCP, and the difference in the implementation status of the BE-LCP by teachers and learning area coordinators.

Table 1. Degree of implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) in terms of curriculum streamlining by the learning area coordinators

Indicative Statements	Learning Area Coordinators (n=5)		
	\bar{x}	SD	QI
Conducted school-based orientation/mentoring and coaching on curriculum review, contextualization, localization and implementation	3.6	0.55	To a very large extent
Provided trainings for teachers on MELCs unpacking and sub tasking for broad cover topics.	3.4	0.55	To a very large extent
Conducted online trainings workshop on crafting of MELCs-based activity sheets.	2.8	1.10	To a large extent
Assessed the progress of implementation of MELCS.	3.4	0.89	To a very large extent
Provided technical assistance to teachers by conducting workshops through coaching and providing appraisal and feedback on the effective and efficient deliveries of MELCs to ensure quality education.	3.4	0.55	To a very large extent
Engaged everyone in crafting of enhanced and contextualized MELCs for the preparation of LMM in the implementation of learning delivery approaches to be cascaded in the field.	3.4	0.89	To a very large extent
Overall	3.3	0.75	Outstanding/Full implementation

As shown in the first table, the learning area coordinators fully implemented the BE-LCP (\bar{x} =3.33, SD =0.75). They outstandingly implemented almost all aspects in terms of curriculum streamlining. However, it can be gleaned that there is discrepancy when it comes to providing training workshop for teachers on crafting MELCs-based activity sheet as the implementation is to a large extent only (\bar{x} =2.8, SD =1.10).

Table 2. Degree of implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) in terms of curriculum streamlining by the teachers

Indicative Statements	Teachers (n=28)		
	\bar{x}	SD	QI
Attended school-based orientation/mentoring and coaching on curriculum review, contextualization, localization and implementation.	3.52	0.58	To a very large extent
Attended trainings for teachers on MELCs unpacking and sub tasking for broad cover topics.	3.52	0.70	To a very large extent
Participated in online trainings workshop on crafting of MELCs-based activity sheets.	3.44	0.51	To a very large extent
The Learning Area Coordinators monitored the progress of implementation of MELCS.	3.74	0.66	To a very large extent
The Learning Area Coordinators provided technical assistance to teachers by conducting workshops through coaching and providing appraisal and feedback on the effective and efficient deliveries of MELCs to ensure quality education.	3.52	0.70	To a very large extent
The Learning Area Coordinators engaged everyone in the crafting of enhanced and contextualized MELCs for the preparation of LMM in the implementation of learning delivery approaches to be cascaded in the field.	3.70	0.67	To a very large extent
Overall	3.57	0.63	Outstanding/Full implementation

The second table yields that the teachers fully implemented all aspects of the BE-LCP on curriculum streamlining ($\bar{x}=3.57$, $SD=0.63$). The table underscores that the teachers attended school-based orientation/mentoring and coaching on curriculum review, contextualization, localization and implementation. As well as the participation on MELCs unpacking and sub tasking and in crafting MELCs-based activity sheets. It can also be gleaned that the Learning Area Coordinators monitored the progress of the implementation of MELCs and provided technical assistance to teachers by conducting workshops through coaching and providing appraisal and feedback on the effective and efficient deliveries of MELCs to ensure quality education.

Table 3. *Difference in the implementation of BE-LCP between the teachers and learning area coordinators*

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
Learning Area Coordinators	3.43	5	.43161	.601	4	.580
Teachers	3.29	27	.51031			

Table 3 reveals that there is no significant difference in the overall implementation of BE-LCP between teachers and learning area coordinators ($p=.580$). From the results gathered on the previous tables discussed, it is notable that most of the responses from the teachers and learning area coordinators are largely related. Both groups agree that the degree of the overall implementation of the BE-LCP does not vary.

This implies that both teachers and learning area coordinators seem to have a similar understanding of the BE-LCP. This suggests a level of alignment and communication regarding the program within the school. Also, the absence of significant difference opens the door for collaborative efforts to further enhance the implementation of the BE-LCP. Both teachers and learning area coordinators should work together to identify areas for improvement and develop strategies for more effective program execution.

The study of Forssten Seiser and Portfelt (2024) promotes the creation of healthy environments in the form of arrangements that create spaces where equivalent collaborations, shared responsibility, and co-ownership may grow.

Tables 1 and 2 indicate the degree of the implementation of BE-LCP in terms of curriculum streamlining between the teachers and the learning area coordinators. Both groups reported that the implementation of BE-LCP on curriculum streamlining is fully implemented on a very large extent. However, there is a gap between the implementation of the Learning Area Coordinators in conducting online trainings workshop on crafting of MELCs-based activity sheets. This implies that the teachers might benefit from additional training or resources to develop the skills on curriculum streamlining, which are essential in translating broad learning competencies into concrete learning activities.

This supports the claim of Amadi (2008) that a good in-service training should, via workshop, conference and study groups improve the quality of programming for the development of teachers in service. Similarly, adequate training for teachers yield multiple benefits as a tool for enhancing teachers' personal and professional development, as well as improving teacher practice and the quality of teaching materials (Duraku, Blakaj, Likaj, Boci, & Shtylla, 2022).

Moreover, both the teachers and learning area coordinators agree that the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) is fully implemented in a very large extent. This high level of implementation may be attributed to the efficacy of the steps that both groups undertaken when it comes to curriculum streamlining. However, further trainings and conferences are encouraged to be conducted by the learning area coordinators. The top administration together with the teachers may work collaboratively to review the BE-LCP for contextualization and localization which supports the recommendation of Urbano (2019) that the alignment of curriculum, instruction and assessment should be strictly observed in the realization of educational goals of the curriculum.

Conclusions

The crafting of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) served to provide a robust framework for continuing education during disruptions, benefiting both educators and students by maintaining educational quality and ensuring that learning progresses seamlessly. Despite the overall success, there is a noted gap in the implementation concerning online training workshops for developing MELCs-based activity sheets. This indicates that while the broader curriculum adjustments are well-handled, specific skills related to creating detailed, competency-based activities need further enhancement among teachers. Ensuring that educators receive ongoing professional development through workshops, conferences, and collaborative study groups is essential. This helps in translating broad learning objectives into effective, localized teaching practices, thereby improving overall educational quality and student outcomes.

Hence, the encouragement for further training and conferences from the school leaders indicates an ongoing need for professional growth. Proactively seeking out and participating in these opportunities can help the teachers stay updated with best practices and innovative strategies in education.

References

Aggarwal, R. & Ranganathan, P. (2019). Study designs: Part 2 – Descriptive studies. https://doi/10.4103/picr.PICR_154_18

Amadi, M. N. (2008). In-service training and professional development of teachers in Nigeria: Through open and distance education. Pre-service and in-service teacher training & learning and teaching styles.

Arrieta, G. (2020). The Experiences Of Junior High School Teachers In Online Teaching And Learning During Enchanced Community Quarantine: Inputs For The Learning Continuity Plan For The New Normal In Education. In K. A. PF (Ed.), *New Normal: Idealism and Implementation in Indonesia and the Philippines* (pp. 383-404). Bali, Indonesia: Jayapangus Press Books. Retrieved from <https://drive.google.com/file/d/13ouJ0YzTZDCoFBk-PUaHTsIZwvdQaoWa/view>

Bukhari, S.A. (2011) What is Comparative Study? <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1962328>

Department of Education. (2020b July 20). Policy guidelines for the provision of learning resources in the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/07/20/july-20-2020-do-018-s-2020-policy-guidelines-for-the-provision-of-learning-resources-in-the-implementation-of-the-basic-education-continuity-plan/>

DepEd Order No. 012 and 013 (2020). Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for Private and Public Schools, Available online at www.deped.gov.ph

Duraku, Z. H., Blakaj, V., Likaj, E.S., Boci, L., & Shtylla, H. (2022). Professional training improves early education teachers' knowledge, skills, motivation, and self-efficacy. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.980254>

Forssten Seiser, A., & Portfelt, I. (2022). Critical aspects to consider when establishing collaboration between school leaders and researchers: two cases from Sweden. *Educational Action Research*, 32(2), 260–275. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09650792.2022.2110137>

Manire, R.N. (2021). Promoting Learning Amidst Pandemic. A Thematic Content Analysis on the Curriculum Management of the Department of Education of the Philippines' Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). DOI.org/10.37467/gka-revedu.v9.2799

Ordinario, A.T. (2022). Challenges and Implementation of The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in The Lens of Elementary Teachers: Basis for Enhancing School-Based Management Operation. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360702308_CHALLENGES_AND_IMPLEMENTATION_OF_THE_BASIC_EDUCATION_LEARNING_CONTINUITY_PLAN_IN_THE_LENS_OF_ELEMENTARY_TEACHERS_BASIS_FOR_ENHANCING_SCHOOL-BASED_MANAGEMENT_OPERATION

Rabor, J.N., Barredo, E.S., Opinio, K.M., & Carmona, V. (2022). Implementation of Learning Continuity Plan: A Basis for a Sustainable Development Program. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7719/jpair.v47i1.570>

Urbano, D.P. (2019). Alignment of Learning Competencies, Instruction and Summative Assessment in Mathematics 10: A Basis for Curriculum Implementation Monitoring Plan

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Gledy Mae Valdez-La Corda
St. Mary's University – Philippines